

Missed Crusted Scabies

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Citation: Sonali Gupta, Shreya K, Dinesh P Asati, Mukesh Kumar Sahni. Missed Crusted Scabies. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(10):1-5.

Received Date: 23 April, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 27 April, 2023; **Published Date:** 28 April, 2023

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ABSTRACT

Crusted scabies have varied clinical presentations and can be missed. Underlying dermatological or neuropsychiatric conditions are usually associated. Lesions of Discoid lupus erythematosus can cause decreased cutaneous sensation predisposing the individual to crusted scabies. Scalp involvement is not uncommon in adults and should be recognised promptly to avoid treatment failures.

Keywords : Crusted scabies , Mite, Scalp , Discoid lupus erythematosus, Treatment failure

BACKGROUND

Crusted scabies has unusual presentations and are often missed. Most of the times scalp is overlooked as cutaneous involvement in the scalp among adult patients is rarely a manifestation of scabies. Due to the common belief that scabies does not infest the scalp, this area might be missed during treatment, leading to treatment failures.

CASE REPORT

A female patient in her fifties presented to dermatology OPD with complaints of generalised itching with visible areas of hyperpigmentation and hyperkeratosis since past 2 years . She described pruritis , severe in intensity, disturbing her sleep that had exacerbated in the past 3 months . The hyperpigmented scaly plaque was believed to have initially started from the chest that progressed to involve the rest of the body including the scalp. On enquiry patient gives history of bilateral asymmetrical knee pain since 5 months with no history of morning stiffness and low grade intermittent fever with no chills and rigors in the past month.

Patient had history of underlying anxiety disorder with no other defined precipitating factors with no seasonal variation. There was no history of any application of topical medication , cosmetics or airborne allergens. No previous surgeries except for tubectomy.

On examination patient was poorly nourished, lean built female . Her Cardiac, pulmonary and musculoskeletal examination also did not reveal any remarkable abnormalities. On cutaneous examination patient was had lichenified fine minimally adherent scaly plaques distributed over scalp, face, trunk and bilateral extremities involving more than 90% of body surface area with few areas of depigmentation and crusting over bilateral upper limbs and thighs (Figure 1A,B,C,D) . Follicular plugging was appreciated on scalp with decreased hair

density and positive carpet tack sign. Clinical diagnosis of Discoid lupus erythematosus was made and her serum was positive for antinuclear antibody.

In the mean time , outbreak of typical scabies was observed in patients admitted in ward along with their attendants and health care personnel's. Cause for the outbreak was evaluated and everyone affected was given topical permethrin along with ivermectin leading to subsidence of their itching. Coincidentally our patient also had improvement in her itching raising suspicion of crusted scabies and the reason for outbreak and was evaluated.

Skin scrapings from the lichenified plaque and from the scalp were viewed under a light microscope coverslip with immersion oil and eggs of sarcoptes scabiei were observed. Ten percent (10%) potassium hydroxide was also applied on a sample of scrapings obtained from the plaque present over chest and scalp and viewed under the light microscope. This test was negative for fungal hyphae. Hence a diagnosis of scabies was made.

Routine investigations of the patient was found to be normal . Skin biopsy showed (Figure 2A,B,C) marked hyperkeratosis and parakeratosis with extravasation of erythrocytes in the stratum corneum, granular layer is attenuated. There was mild spongiosis and focal vacuolization of basal keratinocytes with irregular elongation of rete ridges. Superficial dermis showed moderate perivascular and periadnexal mixed inflammatory infiltrate comprising of mostly lymphocytes, plasma cells, neutrophils and eosinophils with edema, pigment incontinence and extravasation of RBCs in the papillary dermis suggestive of psoriasiform dermatitis.

Diagnosis of crusted scabies with underlying discoid lupus erythematosus was made and patient was started on oral ivermectin given on day 1,2,8,9 ,15 with topical permethrin with marked improvement. Patient was started on Tab Hydroxychloroquine 200mg BD later.

Figure 1A: Areas of depigmentation and crusting over scalp

Figure 1 B: Areas of hyperkeratotic papules with depigmented areas interspersed over trunk

Figure 1C: Bilateral lower limbs showing similar morphology

Figure 2A: Hyperkeratosis and parakeratosis with pseudoepitheliomatous hyperplasia

Figure 2B: Mild spongiosis and focal vacuolization of basal keratinocytes . Superficial dermis showed moderate perivascular and periadnexal mixed inflammatory infiltrate with edema, pigment incontinence and extravasation of RBCs in the papillary dermis

Figure 2C: Infiltrate comprising of mostly lymphocytes, plasma cells,

DISCUSSION

Crusted scabies was described by Boeck and Danielssen in Norway in 1848^[1] in patients of leprosy. It typically develops in patients with defective T-cell immune response or decreased cutaneous sensation. It is seen in immunocompromised and in those who are mentally or physically handicapped. Chronic hepatitis C infection ,dermatomyositis, leukaemia, lymphoma, systemic lupus erythematosus, and trisomy 21 are other conditions in which crusted scabies have been described. As compared to normal patients with scabies with average of 11 mites/individual , patients with Norwegian scabies have innumerable number of mites. Scabies surreptitious is another name described for atypical presentation of scabies that includes crusted scabies as well.

Crusted scabies is characterized by extensive hyperkeratosis and crusting of the skin and erythema and scaling are variable but may evolve into erythroderma. Pruritus can be moderate to severe. Acral distribution is characteristically seen in crusted scabies especially on the palms and soles with involvement of nails and remains the cause for relapse. Atypical manifestations are not uncommon with involvement of localized sites such as scalp^[2], face, penis, finger, tonsil or soles.

Microscopic examination remains diagnostic that reveals numerous mites, eggs and mite faeces (scybala). Epiluminescence microscopy^[3] and high-resolution videodermatoscopy, standard dermatoscopy are non-invasive techniques that can be used to visualize the mite. Eosinophilia is seen in 58% of affected patients. The serum immunoglobulin E levels were also raised in patients with crusted scabies in contrast to scabies. Histopathology^[4] can also be used to diagnose scabies.

Prolonged and persistent treatment is needed in crusted scabies. Multiple doses of Oral ivermectin is effective with topical scabidals. Nails should be trimmed and brushed with topical scabidals. Keratolytic agents can also be used. Mean duration for cure is 3 weeks.

Case reports pertaining to crusted scabies in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus have been described but there are no case reports available in patients with discoid lupus erythematosus.

It is not uncommon for involvement of scalp in patients with crusted scabies in adults. Most of the times scalp is overlooked in crusted scabies^[2]. A KOH smear from the affected scalp is reliable diagnostic tool to identify the adult mites and/or their ova. Treatment to the affected scalp should also be provided as it can lead to treatment failures. When the diagnosis of Crusted scabies is delayed or no adequate isolation of the patient is provided, the highly contagious condition usually results in outbreaks of typical scabies among patients and health care personnel in hospitals and family members at home.

Crusted scabies seems to be underdiagnosed due to its atypical clinical presentations. Our case highlights the atypical presentation of crusted scabies with primary scalp involvement and need for recognizing and appropriately treating this condition.

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